

HORIZON 2020

Research and Innovation action

Grant Agreement No. 730965

ARICE: Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium:

**A strategy for meeting the needs for marine-based research
in the Arctic**

Deliverable 3.2

**Webinar recording on pre-cruise preparation and risk
reduction**

Submission of Deliverable

Work Package	Educating a new generation of polar researchers and professionals
Deliverable no. & title	3.2 Webinar recording on pre-cruise preparation and risk reduction
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Abstract

In the frame of WP3 “Educating a new generation of polar researchers and professionals”, APECS and IOPAN held a first webinar with the topic “Pre-cruise preparation and risk reduction” on 19 February 2019.

Webinar recording on “Pre-cruise preparation and risk reduction”

Speakers

As speakers, we invited researchers with experience in leading cruises on ice-breaking research vessels, namely:

Dr Agnieszka Beszczynska-Möller, physical oceanographer at the Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences (IOPAN) with extensive experience as a cruise leader of multiple Arctic scientific expeditions, talked about planning ship-based and long-term oceanographic field studies and pre-cruise logistics.

Dr Allison Fong, biological oceanographer and microbial ecologist at the Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI), is a coordinator of the ecosystem team in MOSAiC and talked about planning large-scale sea ice and oceanographic research, and the challenges of combining multiple interests of different scientific teams during expeditions.

Dr Monika Kędra, biological oceanographer and ecologist from IOPAN, shared her practical experience on planning and preparing Arctic multidisciplinary research with a main focus on marine ecology and biological oceanography. The webinar provides advice and shares good practices with early career researchers who are planning their field research and cruise sampling.

Participants

54 participants registered in advance to the webinar, but some of them (namely from USA) could not connect due to the huge time difference and asked for the webinar recording. On the webinar day, 20 participants actually connected, 11 of them based at European countries and 9 at non European countries, taking the opportunity to listen and discuss live the planning of ship-based research.

Nationalities of the participants attending the webinar.

Cameroon	1
Norway	1
Germany	5
Brazil	1
Poland	1
Austria	1

United Arab Emirate	2
Italy	2
Argentina	1
Canada	1
South Africa	1
Chile	1
Russian Federation	1
Luxembourg	1

Link:

This webinar was the first out of a webinar series of four. A recording as well as the presented slides are freely available on the ARICE website:

<https://arice.eu/training/webinars/61-arice-webinar-pre-cruise-preparation-and-risk-reduction>